

CoARA Action Plan

R&D portrait of OTH Amberg-Weiden:

With 4,200 students and 117 professors, the Ostbayerische Technische Hochschule (OTH) Amberg-Weiden is a research-strong and STEM-focused university of applied sciences (UAS) in the Upper Palatinate (northern Bavaria). Since its foundation 30 years ago, OTH Amberg-Weiden has seen itself as a UAS in the region and for the region, with a supra-regional and international reach. The four areas of expertise Energy and Resource Efficiency, Information and Communication Technology, Healthcare Management and Medical Technology as well as a Weiden Business School within the framework of Economics are anchored at two locations and four faculties and are implemented in a practice-orientated and application-oriented manner in numerous research activities with a third-party funding volume of around € 11 million per year. OTH Amberg-Weiden reached a special milestone in 2023 when the Bavarian State Ministry of Science and the Arts awarded the university the right to award doctoral degrees for two strong research topics, specifically for the R&D topics 'Resource Efficiency and Digitalisation' and 'Digital Innovations for a Changing Society', on the basis of two successful applications as part of a Bavaria-wide process.

As part of its legal mandate, OTH Amberg-Weiden is responsible for ensuring good scientific practice in research and teaching. The guidelines for safeguarding good scientific practice (<https://www.oth-aw.de/forschung/forschungsprofil/forschungsgrundsaeetze/richtlinien-zur-sicherung-guter-wissenschaftlicher-praxis/>) serve as the basis for this. They are based on the German Research Foundations 'Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice' from August 2019. In addition, sustainable development is understood and anchored as an overall institutional approach at OTH Amberg-Weiden. It attaches great importance to integrity and ethical behaviour in research and is therefore also a member of the Joint Ethics Committee of Bavarian UAS (GEHBA) (<https://www.gehba.de/home/>).

Overall, OTH Amberg-Weiden, as a technical university of applied sciences since 2013, considers practice-orientated research to be a core task and implies the importance of a responsible research culture. For this reason, research is not only promoted, but the integrity of research is also prioritised and the development of each individual researcher is supported. It actively supports the principles of open science and encourages researchers to disclose their findings in order to promote collaboration and maximise the impact of research. This is based on a positive research culture that emphasises collaboration, interdisciplinarity and outreach to address societal challenges through research.

OTH Amberg-Weiden is in favour of qualitative assessment becoming more important in the evaluation of research, whereby peer review can play a central role. Quantitative indicators will continue to be used responsibly. The overall aim is to ensure a comprehensive assessment of research and researchers, taking into account different types of outcomes, practices and activities, while considering the influence of different career paths and personal circumstances on the quality and impact of research.

OTH Amberg-Weiden endeavours to continuously improve and make valuable national and international contributions in the field of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). To achieve this goal, participation in the National Chapter Germany is an essential building block.

The current status and specific challenges are summarised below:

Research assessment to date:

Quantitative:

- **Teaching reduction for research:** on the basis of third-party funds received, publications, other activities such as patents, review activities, etc.:
Internal research professorships: retroactively on the basis of research achievements over a period of 5 years
Project research professorships: on the basis of short and medium-term research concepts in the next 3 years
- **Research allowance** and/or special performance-related pay: on the basis of acquired industrial research contracts
- **Own right to award doctoral degrees:** awarded in 2023 on the basis of acquired third-party funds, publications, other activities such as patents, review activities, supervision of cooperative doctoral degrees)
- **Leave of absence for research and practice**

=> Different assessments in STEM fields and economics (publications are rated higher here than third-party funding income)

Qualitative:

- Publications on: Homepage, social media, press releases
- Internal university award: EXCELLENT
- Annual research report of the OTH Amberg-Weiden
- Enabling the foundation of an in-house institute (with qualitative evaluation)
- Enabling the foundation of a competence centre (including qualitative evaluation)

Strategies implemented:

- Guiding principles
- Guidelines for safeguarding good scientific practice (in accordance with the German Research Foundation's guidelines)
- Anchoring sustainability in research
- Internationalisation strategy
- OTH Amberg-Weiden development plan 2023 - 2030
- Target agreements and university of applied sciences contract with the Bavarian State Ministry of Science and the Arts 2023 - 2027 (with predecessors)

Current approaches in research development:

Orientation of research towards the following three aspects as a prerequisite for continued practice-orientated research and successful transfer to industry and society:

- **Publicity:** R&D results are publicised in a variety of ways and in a range of forms to both the scientific and non-scientific community. In this context, a 100% position (E 13) for science communication was created at OTH Amberg-Weiden in the Institute for Applied Research in September 2024. Selected examples of R&D communication are: Annual research report, research forum, research forums from the four faculties, annual report, homepage, conferences (also international), lecture series, lecture events, press and public relations work, Science Night, academic celebration, annual conference of the East Bavarian universities, Science Day of the European Metropolitan Region Nuremberg (EMN).

- **Application and benefits:** At OTH Amberg-Weiden and its development from a university of applied sciences to a technical university of applied sciences (application-based in a Bavarian-wide competition in 2012/2013), the focus is on the practical orientation of R&D within the framework of knowledge and technology transfer. The cooperations in the transfer have a regional as well as supra-regional and international reach, third-party funds are mainly acquired in cooperation with practice. As part of its application orientation, OTH Amberg-Weiden has now established 5 technology transfer centres in its region, each of which is geared towards a specific R&D/transfer focus and based on regional needs assessments. As part of a 'PartnerCircle', OTH Amberg-Weiden cooperates with 34 regional companies, as well as with 30 innovative learning centres in its university region. These activities are coordinated by an Institute for Applied Research.

- **Sustainability/ethics:** At OTH Amberg-Weiden, the aspects of sustainability and ethics are coordinated in an in-house institute (Institute for Sustainability and Ethics). It follows the principles for sustainability in research of the German Research Foundation and has adopted a guideline for this. OTH Amberg-Weiden is also a member of the Joint Ethics Committee of Bavarian UAS (GEHBa).

As a technical university of applied sciences, OTH Amberg-Weiden focuses on STEM disciplines in its faculties and 54 study programmes.

Social work, health and education disciplines are anchored in the Faculty of Industrial Engineering and Health, here in the degree programmes (Bachelor's and Master's) Medical Technology, Physician Assistance, Medical Engineering, Digital Healthcare Management and the part-time Master's degree programme in Medical Law. The establishment of a nursing degree programme is planned. OTH Amberg-Weiden cooperates with a large number of medical and healthcare institutions, such as clinics. [Research in the social work, health and education area, especially in social work and education, will be further expanded.](#)

Both STEM and social work, health and education area are included in the OTH Amberg-Weiden's doctoral programme for the two R&D focus areas 'Resource efficiency and digitalisation' and 'Digital innovations for a changing society'.

The IOOI model (Input - Output - Outcome - Impact) is known and partially applied as an impact chain for technical, economic and social innovations in both STEM and social work, health and education subjects. The aim is to increase the use of the IOOI model.

Action Plan along the guiding questions and the 10 core commitments of CoARA:

1) Recognise the diversity of contributions:

Current status:

- The criteria for applicants are professional, pedagogical and personal suitability.
- In addition to the academic profile, practical experience, previous research achievements and networks are also taken into account.

Actions and goals:

- Workshops with researchers at all career levels
- 'career4Prof' programme for early career researchers
- Further strengthening of internationality
- Support through targeted further training programmes

Time horizon:

Two junior professorships were appointed. Junior professorship serves to fulfil the qualification requirements (especially practical experience) for a full professorship and will be achieved within 3 years.

2) Qualitative evaluation with peer review supported by quantitative indicators

Current status:

- Quantitative (mainly) and qualitative metrics are available and used in R&D
- Quantitative: Budget/third-party funds, projects, publications, conference contributions, patents and inventions, scientific staff, doctoral students, annual reports from the institutes
- Qualitative: Sustainability, integration of R&D results into teaching

Actions and goals:

- Increase the use of qualitative indicators in research, development and transfer

Time horizon:

Term of the current university development plan of OTH Amberg-Weiden 2023 - 2030, term of the target agreements or the university contract with the Bavarian State Ministry of Science and the Arts 2023 - 2027.

3) Use of publication-based metrics, e.g. H-Index or JF

Publication-based metrics are not currently used and will not be used in the future. Publications are divided into peer-reviewed and non-peer-reviewed and recorded accordingly.

4) Use of rankings in research assessment

Rankings are not currently used in research assessment and will not be used in the future.

In its annual rankings, the Centre for Higher Education Development (CHE, Gütersloh) takes into account, among other things, the research performance of the faculties included (third-party funding, doctorates).

5) Provision of resources for the reform of research assessment

Current status:

- Resources are made available for the planning and implementation of the CoARA action plan
- Expertise and networking with the relevant units is in place
- Networking activities and science communication, including support for start-ups, are in place. A position (E 13, 100%) set up for science communication at OTH Amberg-Weiden is financed from the UAS contract with the Bavarian State Ministry of Science and the Arts.

Actions and goals:

- Resources are provided by the UAS management, the extended UAS management and in part also by the university council. Annual strategy conferences (lasting 2 days) are also organised for this purpose.

Time horizon:

Term of the current university development plan of OTH Amberg-Weiden 2023 - 2030, term of the target agreements or the university contract with the Bavarian State Ministry of Science and the Arts 2023 - 2027.

6) Review and development of criteria, instruments and procedures for research assessment (e.g. narrative, competence-based, evidence-based CV, diversification of research careers and associated career development)

Current status:

- Evaluation of research within the UAS takes place and is taken into account in reduction of teaching (here also internal research professorships and project research professorships)
- Quantitative indicators are currently decisive (also in the evaluation of the technology transfer centres)
- Comprehensive advisory, financial, spatial and administrative support for research is provided and is continuously customised

Actions and goals:

- Workshops with researchers at all career stages, including networking events with doctoral students
- Impact thinking is to be strengthened and a framework for the social impact of R&D is to be developed
- Expand the framework for qualitative assessment of research, development and transfer (including diversity in CVs)

- Increase the visibility of R&D competences by expanding science communication

Time horizon:

Term of the current university development plan of OTH Amberg-Weiden 2023 - 2030, term of the target agreements or the university contract with the Bavarian State Ministry of Science and the Arts 2023 - 2027.

7) Raising awareness of the reform, transparent communication, guidance and training on evaluation criteria and procedures and their application

Current status:

- Integration of the topic into the research forum with the professors
- Homepage, internal university process portal
- Integration of the topic into the network meetings with doctoral candidates and the corresponding qualification programmes at the Doctoral Centre
- Sensitisation with regard to the specialist articles in the research report

Actions and goals:

- Internal communication with the researchers
- Information events and workshops, also within the framework of science communication

Time horizon:

The target time horizon is 2028.

8) Exchange of practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and outside the coalition

Actions and goals:

- Within CoARA: OTH Amberg-Weiden has joined the National Chapter Germany, which offers a network and support
- If necessary, participation in corresponding CoARA working groups to exchange information about existing national and international networks
- Exchange of knowledge, mutual learning and discussions from the perspective of a technical university of applied sciences
- Outside of CoARA: Discussion of CoARA in the TBHAW (working group of transfer centres at universities of applied sciences in Bavaria)

9) Communication of progress on compliance with the principles and implementation of the commitments

Actions and goals:

Communication via the relevant channels (as under 7.), e.g. homepage, internal process portal, R&D information events

10) Evaluation of practices, criteria and tools based on sound evidence and the latest research and publication of data for evidence gathering and research

Current status:

- Publicly funded R&D/transfer projects are presented via the homepage and also via press work
- Annual research report of the OTH Amberg-Weiden (around 200 pages)
- Reports on the R&D results to the project sponsors/clients

Actions and goals:

- The aim is to establish a centralised research data management, possibly in a network of UAS in Bavaria, based on the research information systems (RIS)
- The aim is a cycle of 3 years, based on the application of the research priorities of the universities of applied sciences to the HRK German Rectors' Conference (HRK research map)